

Ecolinguistics Study on Balinese Lexicons of *Memande* at Celuk Village Gianyar, Bali, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT: The study on Balinese lexicons related to *Memande* (silver and gold smith) at Celuk Village in Gianyar Bali concerned with the types of lexicons use in: the materials, tools, products, and activities of the silver and goldsmiths. The study is field research in which the data were gathered in the field by applying in-depth interviews and observation with the silver and gold smiths. The theories of eco-linguistics and sociolinguistics were applied to analyse the data. The findings showed that there were 21 lexicons of tools, 5 lexicons of material, 25 lexicons of products, and 19 lexicons of activities.

KEYWORDS: Ecolinguistics, Lexicon, *Memande*

INTRODUCTION

As a tourist destination, Bali is famous for its natural beauty as well as its unique and very attractive culture, so it becomes a tourist attraction. Cultural tourism developed in Bali makes a dominant contribution to the economy of the Balinese people as a whole. The dynamics of tourism development in Bali provide opportunities for all economic potential for the Balinese people, including crafts which include crafts made of precious metals such as jewelry, and other tools made of gold and silver. Jewelry such as; bracelets, rings, necklaces, and tools related to religious ceremonies in Bali, are generally made by *Pande* residents, especially the gold and silver *Pande* residents.

Haugen (1972) reveals that language resides in the mind of the speaker and functions as a liaison between the speaker and the social and natural environment. The environment of a language is language speakers with social and cultural backgrounds because it is impossible to understand a language without its speakers. This is in accordance with the assessment of the vitality of language (UNESCO2003:1) which states that language differences are important for human heritage. Each language represents the unique cultural policies of its speakers so the extinction of a language is the destruction of its people.

Economic developments, technology, and modernization have a major influence on the lexicon related to *memande* activities. Economically, many *Pande* residents switch professions to ones that are more economically profitable, technological developments result in changes in the tools used to carry out the activities, and modernization affects the types of products produced.

Wakhyuninggarshi (2018) in the History of Celuk Silver Handicrafts in Gianyar reveals that in 1915 silver craft in Celuk Village, Gianyar was pioneered by a *Pande* named I Nyoman Gati. I Nyoman Gati learned from his father, I Nyoman Klesir, who previously learned from a *Pande* family, Pan Sumpang in Mengwi, Badung Regency. I Nyoman Gati and his students initially worked on silver handicrafts only for the purposes of ritual facilities in Bali, such as *bokoran*, *sangku*, *caratan* or *penastan*, *kris*, and women's accessories for weddings.

Then this profession of *memande* developed and could improve the welfare of the family which was then followed by other people (who were not descendants of *pande*) in Celuk Village. This is because the products produced by I Nyoman Gati and his students were favored by the King of Gianyar at that time, so he was trusted to work in *puri-puri* (noble houses). In 1935 the silver and goldsmiths' profession in Celuk village grew and the products produced also expanded to include jewelry (accessories) such as rings, earrings, necklaces, bracelets, brooches, etc. Based on this overview it is important to have documentation of the lexicons being used by the *Pande* residents especially the silver and goldsmiths in Celuk. Based on the background of the study, the research is focused on the investigation of the types of Balinese lexicons related to materials, products, and tools that are being used by the silver and goldsmiths at Celuk Village.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The methods used to obtain the data in this study were direct observation (participant observation), in-depth interviews, and documentation studies. The informants who were selected as resource persons or information providers in this study were the

head village, elderly residents of silver and goldsmiths, and the younger generation whose profession as silver and goldsmith at Celuk Village, Sukawati District, Gianyar Regency.

The selection of informants was carried out using a purposive technique, namely by selecting the key informant (head of the village), as he knows more about the situation of the silver and goldsmiths at Celuk. Furthermore, by positioning the key informant, a snowball technique was used. That is, from informants; the identities of other informants needed in this study were extracted. It was the key informant who provided information about the types of lexicons related to the Balinese Lexicon on *Memande* (silver and goldsmiths).

Interview and observation techniques were also used in this study. However, the type of interview, in this case, is in-depth interviews, especially interviews about individual experiences which are usually referred to as methods of using individual life history data or human documents (Koentjaraningrat, 1989:158). This interview technique is also equipped with regular in-depth interviews on the tools, materials, and products they produced. The data analysis was carried out by descriptive-qualitative analysis, namely by grouping the types of lexicons related to *Memande* activities, tools, materials, and products produced.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Based on the results of the interviews and observation of the places where the gold and silversmiths work at Celuk village. There were two hundred gold and silversmith who work as a part-timer because some of them also work as farmers. During the observation of the workplace as well as the place where the products were being on display for SMEs (small, and medium enterprises), it was found that lexicons related to *Memande* (gold and silversmiths) lexicons used by *Pande* residents are grouped into (1) tool lexicon (2) material lexicon, (3) product lexicon, and (4) activity-related lexicon. The following is an explanation of each of the lexicon groups related to silver and goldsmiths.

The "tool lexicon" is the lexicons related to the tools used by silver and goldsmiths at Celuk Village, Sukawati District, Gianyar Regency to produce products in the form of ceremonial tools, jewelry, and others. Then tools lexicons are shown in Table 1

Tools used in making the products		
No	Balinese	English (gloss translation)
1	<i>kronong</i>	tools to measure metal
2	<i>pemeludan</i>	tools to form wire
3	<i>penyongkel soca</i>	tools to gouge gem stone
4	<i>besi gilik gede</i>	large round shape iron
5	<i>besi gilig cenik</i>	small round shape iron
6	<i>pengotok</i>	tool for flattening metal
7	<i>penyepitan gede</i>	large clamp
8	<i>penyepitan cenik</i>	small clamp
9	<i>gunting slaka</i>	scissors to cut silver or gold
10	<i>palu</i>	hammer
11	<i>pengaudan</i>	tools to stretch metal
12	<i>predom</i>	tools to smoothen the metal
13	<i>paron</i>	flat tool
14	<i>blendes kawat</i>	tool for flattening wire
15	<i>blendes bakalan</i>	tool for flattening base material
16	<i>blendes plat</i>	tool for flattening metal (silver or gold)
17	<i>bor</i>	drill
18	<i>kempes</i>	gas pump
19	<i>paet</i>	chisel
20	<i>pengukur bungkung</i>	ring measurement
21	<i>klerek</i>	type of fruit to shine the colour of the metal

The following picture are some of the tools use by the silver and gold smith

besi gilik

penyongkelan

penyepitan

pengotok

pengukur bungkung

pemipih logam

The Material lexicons

Materials that are used by the silver and goldsmiths in producing their products as shown in table 2 bellow:

Table 2

Materials used in making the products		
No	Balinese	English (gloss translation)
1	<i>mas</i>	gold
2	<i>slaka</i>	silver
3	<i>tembaga</i>	copper
4	<i>perunggu</i>	bronze
5	<i>timah</i>	lead

The following are the materials used by the silver and goldsmiths in producing their products

mas(gold)

slaka (silver)

timah (lead)

temaga(copper)

perunggu (bronze)

The Product Lexicons

Product lexicons are all products produced by Pande in their daily life as producers of products made of gold or silver, which are presented in table 3 which is divided into (1) ceremonial products, (2) jewelry products, and (3) ornaments.

The Hindu Rituals Product lexicons

The are many lexicons concerned with the products used in the ceremony conducted by the Balinese Hindus as the following table 3.1

Table 3.1

The Hindu Rituals Product Lexicons		
No	Balinese	English (gloss translation)
1	<i>kadutan</i>	kris
2	<i>Bunga mas</i>	golden flower
3	<i>pretima</i>	effigy
4	<i>pererai</i>	face form ornament for the effigy
5	<i>canting</i>	holy water holder
6	<i>cupu</i>	holy water container
7	<i>ketu</i>	cap for the priest
8	<i>krewista</i>	head ornament placed on the forehead
9	<i>Pengetisan tirta</i>	tool to sprinkle holy water
10	<i>Pupuk</i>	ornament placed on the forehead of the baby

Pratima

bunga mas

cupu

kris

Silver and gold *Pupuk* (ornament placed on the forehead of the baby on the auspicious day of 105 days ceremony)

ketu (headgear for Hindu priests) made of gold

Pengetisan tirta

krawista (ornament placed on the forehead when a person is conducting a purification ceremony)

The Lexicons of Jewelry Products

There are many types of products of jewelry either silver or gold, as Celuk village is well-known for its handcraft on jewelry. The following are the lists of lexicons shown in table 3.2

Table 3.2

The jewelry Product Lexicons		
No	Balinese	English (gloss translation)
1	<i>petitis</i>	headgear for women used during the ceremony
2	<i>kalung</i>	neckless
3	<i>gelang</i>	bracelet
4	<i>bungkung</i>	ring
5	<i>cucuk</i>	hairpin
6	<i>bros</i>	brioche
7	<i>anting</i>	earrings
8	<i>socan kalung</i>	Pendant

Celuk village is famous for its jewelry (silver and gold) there are many types of each, the following pictures are some of the pieces of jewelry.

bungkung (ring)

Socan kalung (silver and gold pendants)

kalung mas, kalung slaka (silver and gold neckless)

anting (earrings)

The Lexicons of Household Ornaments

In recent years, there are some modifications to the products related to household ornaments in various forms, the following table 3.3

Table 3.3

The household ornament product Lexicons		
No	Balinese	English (gloss translation)
1	<i>togog mas</i>	golden statue
2	<i>togog gajah</i>	elephant statue
3	<i>tongos tisu</i>	tissue case
4	<i>wadah manisan</i>	candy container
5	<i>barang-barongan</i>	barang like ornament
6	<i>replika rangka</i>	rangda replica
7	<i>ornament kedis</i>	birds ornament

Togog geruda

tongos tisu

togog gajah

The Activity Lexicons

Lexicon of activities correlated to activities carried out while working on goods or products made by *Pande*; The activity lexicons is associated with all verbs related to the manufacture of products. The following describes the lexicon related to the verb in table 4.

Table 4

Activity lexicons		
No	Balinese	English gloss
1	<i>ngelandes</i>	metal flattening activity
2	<i>ngebor</i>	the activity of perforating the material
3	<i>ngunting</i>	tutting with scissors
4	<i>maet</i>	to sculpt
5	<i>memalu</i>	the activity of hitting materials with a hammer
6	<i>nyepit</i>	pinning
7	<i>ngeblendes</i>	activity turning on the metal heater
8	<i>nyampur</i>	mixing metal materials
9	<i>ngaduk</i>	stirring metal materials
10	<i>ngukir</i>	to carve
11	<i>ngamplas</i>	sandpapering
12	<i>ngetep</i>	to cut
13	<i>ngembonang</i>	to chill
14	<i>mentengin</i>	to flatten
15	<i>nyutsut</i>	to clean
16	<i>nyikat</i>	to brush
17	<i>ngukur</i>	to measure
18	<i>ngalusan</i>	to smoothen
19	<i>ngemem</i>	to soak

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the previous discussion of the Balinese lexicons related to *Memande* (silver and goldsmiths) at Celuk village, there were found the types of lexicons: 5 lexicons of material, 21 lexicons of tools, 25 lexicons of products, and 19 activity lexicons.

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